

UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

Finnish universities are required by national law to have gender equality (GE) and diversity plans (the law requires any organisation employing more than 30 people to have a GE plan and a diversity plan). These plans initially covered mostly gender equality issues and later increasingly also dealt with diversity issues. A national report found that only 45% of universities had their plans up to date, in conformity with the legislative requirement that the plan be updated every second year.¹ The plans also often miss certain required sections, such as an assessment of measures implemented in the previous period.²

The Act on Equality between Women and Men, Section 6, lists a number of areas that an employer is required to act upon and prevent. These include gender-based discrimination, including sexual and gender harassment. Most of the gender equality and diversity plans of Finnish universities deal with sexual and/or gender harassment in some way – for example, by referring to a code of conduct or certain procedures and having harassment contact persons in place.³ However, these references may be very general in the plans and may not be accompanied by any concrete measures or evaluations.

¹ Tanhua, I. (2020). *Report on the promotion of gender equality and non-discrimination in higher education institutions*. Publications of the Ministry of Education and Culture. Finland 2020:24.

² Ibid.

³ Ibid, p. 50.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The University of Helsinki has two main policies which are both non-dedicated policies, that is, more general policies that address GBV as a part of the policy. One is the Equality and Diversity Plan 2021-2024,⁴ in which gender equality and diversity issues are outlined in a relatively broad manner, and GBV is one part of this policy. The Plan addresses the prevention of discrimination and harassment and the prevention of inappropriate behaviour and harassment.

The second policy is a document called the Prevention of Inappropriate Behaviour and Harassment at the University of Helsinki, a set of guidelines⁵ that call for the creation of a staff and student liaison officer and provide more detailed instructions on what staff and students should do if they believe they have witnessed harassment.

URLs

- › The University of Helsinki Equality and Diversity Plan 2021-2024: https://www.helsinki.fi/assets/drupal/2021-05/UH_Equality_Diversity_Plan_2021_2024.pdf
- › The Prevention of Inappropriate Behaviour and Harassment at the University of Helsinki: <https://studies.helsinki.fi/sites/default/files/inline-files/Prevention%20of%20inappropriate%20behaviour%20and%20harassment%20at%20the%20University%20of%20Helsinki.pdf>

Entry into force: The University of Helsinki Equality and Diversity Plan 2021-2024 (2021); The Prevention of Inappropriate Behaviour and Harassment at the University of Helsinki (2016).

TRAINING

Training on how to deal with challenging situations requiring guidance and counselling was organised for teachers and academic administration staff in 2019, 2020, and 2021. These training events have been popular. The training reviews the guidelines mentioned above and discusses harassment from a legal, psychological, and safety perspective. Training on unconscious bias and Pride events are also organised every year. A committee also decides on a specific theme on which to focus each year, which in 2021 was the promotion of antiracism and the inclusion of disability in 2022.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

⁴ https://www.helsinki.fi/assets/drupal/2021-05/UH_Equality_Diversity_Plan_2021_2024.pdf

⁵ Available online at: <https://studies.helsinki.fi/sites/default/files/inline-files/Prevention%20of%20inappropriate%20behaviour%20and%20harassment%20at%20the%20University%20of%20Helsinki.pdf>

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: Both policies cover sexual harassment and gender-based harassment.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: 5Ps are covered – prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, and policy.

While the University of Helsinki Equality and Diversity Plan 2021-2024 covers prevention, protection, prosecution, the Prevention of Inappropriate Behaviour and Harassment at the University of Helsinki covers protection, provision of services and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: Both policies are aimed at academic staff, non-academic staff, and students.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes, the University of Helsinki Equality and Diversity Plan 2021-2024 considers an intersectional perspective.

Specific vulnerable groups: The University of Helsinki Equality and Diversity Plan 2021-2024 addresses LGBTQIA+ staff and students and religious minorities.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The University of Helsinki Equality and Diversity Plan 2021-2024 states in reference to the prevention of harassment that '[T]he guidelines name the staff and student liaison officers and provide more detailed instructions on what staff and students should do if they believe they have witnessed harassment'.

The Prevention of Inappropriate Behaviour and Harassment at the University of Helsinki indicates that the university does not condone any type of inappropriate treatment, bullying, or harassment. Every university supervisor and teacher is obliged to address any harassment they observe taking place in their work or study community. The university provides help in cases where an employee or student encounters inappropriate treatment in their work or studies.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes, in the Prevention of Inappropriate Behaviour and Harassment at the University of Helsinki: 'For those accused of bullying or harassment: If necessary, talk to your supervisor. It is better for him or her to hear about the accusations directly. Even if you think that you are not guilty of bullying or harassment, do not belittle the accuser's feelings, and immediately stop behaving in the allegedly inappropriate manner. You can also discuss the situation with an occupational safety delegate. If you are a student, you can discuss the situation with the Student Union's contact person for harassment.'

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: Yes, HR Services regularly discuss cases brought to its attention and possible measures.

Monitoring: Yes, the HR and Equality and Diversity Committee monitors these procedures annually.

Evaluation: Yes, in the University of Helsinki Equality and Diversity Plan 2021-2024.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The policy that sets out a step-by-step institutional procedure is the Prevention of Inappropriate Behaviour and Harassment at the University of Helsinki.

The policy defines: Who to contact, responsible persons, sanctions.

Student vs student / student vs staff

If students are treated inappropriately, they should tell the bully or harasser immediately that they do not approve of their conduct and that they should stop. It could be that the harasser did not realise that they were acting in an offensive way.

Students may contact the head of their department or the dean or vice-dean in charge of teaching at their faculty. In study-related matters, the discipline coordinator should also be informed of any inappropriate behaviour. If a department or faculty management learns that a student has

subjected other students or staff to harassment or inappropriate behaviour, the management is required to intervene.

If the issue cannot be resolved in the student's own work or study environment, they should seek outside help. Students can contact one of the contact persons for harassment at the Student Union or the Finnish Student Health Service. Students should seek help from the individual or organisation that feels the most natural to them (inappropriate behaviour during extracurricular activities intended for students should primarily be dealt with by the Student Union's contact person for harassment). Students can also contact the university's harassment contact persons.

Students and staff should keep a written record of incidents. The bully or harasser cannot be held accountable if the incidents cannot be proven. Any offensive emails or other messages should be saved. When reporting an incident, it should be described in detail and accompanied by documentation (e.g. an email). Once experience of inappropriate behaviour is reported, the reporting person is required to participate in the proceedings concerning the matter.

The management must clarify the situation by asking both parties for their views on the events and by recording these views. If the situation cannot be resolved through informal, direct discussions and instructions or if the matter is too serious for such instructions to be considered sufficient, the department or faculty may hold a formal hearing.

Where a student is reported for inappropriate behaviour, s/he must be invited to this hearing. The head of the department, the dean, or the vice-dean in charge of teaching must attend. The student must be notified that s/he may request a support person (e.g. from the Student Union) to attend the hearing. The person subjected to inappropriate behaviour and the person who reported it must also be provided the opportunity to attend the hearing and be accompanied by a support person. The purpose of the hearing is to explain to the student how his or her behaviour is unacceptable, how it must change, and what measures will be taken if it does not change. The minutes of the hearing must record the student's and the university's views of the matter as well as the university's instructions to the student. The student must be provided with a copy of the minutes after the hearing. If the student does not attend the hearing despite being invited, the minutes must be based on the information available and must be sent to the student.

If the student's behaviour does not change despite being provided with instructions on doing so or if the matter is serious enough for a hearing to be considered insufficient, disciplinary action will be taken. In such situations, the faculty or department must contact the university's legal counsel specialised in academic affairs, who will then be responsible for preparing and presenting the matter.

In a disciplinary procedure, students may be issued a **written warning** if they

- › disrupt teaching,
- › behave violently or threateningly, or
- › act fraudulently or otherwise violate the university's regulations.

If the student's action or inaction is serious or s/he continues to behave inappropriately after receiving a written warning, the student may be suspended from the university for a fixed period of up to one year. The decision on a written warning must be made by the rector of the university, and the decision on a suspension must be made by the Board of the University. The provisions of the Universities Act on restrictions to student admission apply to first- and second-cycle studies in pharmacy, dentistry, medicine, psychology, and logopedics. The provisions also apply to studies

in social work and teacher education as well as education in psychotherapy. In these fields, a student may be expelled, for example, if:

- › the student has repeatedly or seriously endangered another person's health or safety in their studies and thereby has demonstrated him- or herself to be manifestly unsuitable to perform study-related assignments or traineeships;
- › the student's health or functional capacity manifestly fails to meet the admission requirements of section 37 a, subsection 1 of the Universities Act.

If, in the case of inappropriate behaviour or harassment, the student's field is one of those referred to in the provisions of the Universities Act on expulsion, or if the application of those provisions is considered, the faculty or department must contact the university's legal counsel specialised in academic affairs.

Staff vs staff

University employees may contact an occupational safety delegate, a chief union representative, a contact person for harassment, the Human Resources Development and Occupational Wellbeing Unit, the Occupational Health Unit or the HR manager.

If a person reports an incident to a supervisor or a teacher, it must be described in detail and accompanied by documentation (e.g. an email). Once an experience of inappropriate behaviour has been reported, the complainant is required to participate in the proceedings concerning the matter. The university's contact persons for harassment provide advice and guidance.

The employer is required by law to take action if an employee is subjected to harassment or other inappropriate treatment in the workplace. The supervisor is responsible for clarifying the situation. The Human Resources Development and Occupational Wellbeing Unit and HR managers can support the supervisor in this task. The supervisor must hear the parties involved without bias in order to clarify the course of events. The supervisor will invite the parties involved to meetings, of which minutes must be taken. These discussions must also include an agreement on the measures to be taken and the related monitoring, the details of which are recorded in the minutes. The supervisor must ensure that the agreed measures are taken and monitoring is performed.

If an employee continues to treat others inappropriately or if the inappropriate behaviour is serious, the situation may warrant that measures required under labour law be taken. In that case, the faculty or department must contact an expert at HR Services, who will then be responsible for preparing and presenting the matter. If the bullying or harassment has included an intentional violation of physical integrity or the threat of such a violation, the employee may report this to the police.

Additional information

In addition to the above-mentioned documents, the University of Helsinki also has had Ethical Guidelines since 2020, which together with the other principles constitute a foundation for decision-making and operational development at the university. Lastly, the university has Social Media Guidelines, which offer advice on how to engage in online and digital activities in a safe and responsible manner, and includes first-aid measures for cases of social media harassment in the Flamma intranet. When necessary, the university's communications department will help to hide social media accounts, and it can, as a form of first aid, help by going through and storing messages. The key message of the new guidelines is that the university wants to encourage

researchers, teachers, and employees to be active on social media. The document contains tips for experts, advice on questions related to identity and responsibility, instructions arising from legislation, and information on university practices, hashtags, and support services.

The Ethical Guidelines addresses the role of bystanders. The university-wide ethical guidelines provide written instructions pertaining to fundamental topics, such as human rights, academic freedom, equality, and sustainable operations. The key topics of the guidelines are based on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the sustainable development goals in Agenda 2030 of the United Nations. The university also takes a strong stance in all of its operations to protect democracy as a form of society, academic freedom, and the autonomy of universities. Likewise, all members of the university community are equal, and the university does not condone any inappropriate behaviour.

- › Ethical Guidelines: <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/about-us/responsibility-and-sustainability/ethical-guidelines>
- › Social Media Guidelines: <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/news/university-social-media/social-media-guidelines>

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

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